

Securing P4-SDN Data Plane against Flow Table Modification Attack

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Abstract—Security in Software Defined Network (SDN) architecture is becoming the most substantial challenge. This paper introduces a novel threat model focused on flow table modification in the P4-programmable SDN data plane, outlining an attacker’s stochastic manipulation of flow rules from a compromised switch. A detection framework is proposed to identify the malicious switch within the network by utilizing the thrift port. Moreover, a fuzzy-rule-based mitigation strategy has been proposed to identify the severity of attacks. The feasibility and effectiveness of the methodology are evaluated using a developed testbed setup by employing Facebook datacenter fabric topology in a Mininet emulator and BMv2 switch.

Index Terms—SDN, Flow table security, Flow rule modification attack, P4 switch, Data plane.

I. INTRODUCTION

Software-defined networking (SDN) is a promising network architecture with numerous advantages to meet massive-scale future and automated network management demand. The control layer of SDN contains a control application with a software-driven controller that centralizes and organizes the configurations of the network switches in the data plane layer [1], [2]. Every forwarding device has a flow table, and each flow table stores a set of flow entries in SDN [3]. Each incoming packet is examined, and proper action is taken based on the flow entries. The advancement in programmable forwarding devices facilitate programming packet-processing behaviour in the data plane of the SDN network. In recent times, domain-specific network programming languages such as Network Programming Language (NPL) and Programming Protocol-independent Packet Processors (P4) are utilized by the data planes [4], [5]. The P4 allows the forwarding and processing packets in the data plane without requiring intervention from the control plane. The ecosystem delivers a wider scope to solve networking problems that are considered challenging in traditional switches. The primary benefit of the P4 switch over the OF switch is the programmable pipeline and flexibility. Moreover, OF doesn’t provide complete protocol neutrality [6]. In the remaining part, we used the P4-programmable switch and the P4-SDN switch interchangeably.

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Fig. 1: A representative attack scenario with compromised P4 switch in SDN datacenter network.

Over the years, popular SDN controllers, including ODL, Floodlight allows system administrators to interact with the REST API and insert policies into the controller using a curl-like simple command-line tool for data transfer [7]. These policies are derived from the rules inserted remotely or locally in the OF applications with the southbound interface. Being aware of the shortcomings of the controller, the attacker may employ a bot that acts as a man-in-middle attacker which can control the flow entries [8], [9]. Consider Fig. 1 where a flow table modification scenario has demonstrated using a compromised P4 switch in an SDN-assisted datacenter network. An attack from a malicious switch is performed to modify the action pair of existing rules and allocate new flow rules to process the packet forwarding flows. Unfortunately, if the attacker modifies the flow rules, the controller is not aware of it. According to [10], if multiple switches experience flow rule modification attacks, it can lead to a Distributed Denial of Services (DDoS) attack [11]. For instance, alteration of the matching key and action pair $\langle 10.0.1.12 - Forward \rangle$ can generate large packet forwarding requests. If multiple existing flow rules experience the same modification, it can lead to a DDoS attack. Such a scenario motivates us to design a feasible solution for detecting and mitigating flow rule modification attacks in the SDN control plane.

The prime contributions of this paper are outlined below.

- This study introduces a new possible flow table modifica-

tion attack framework for the P4-programmable SDN data plane. The detection mechanism of the proposed framework backtracks the existing flow rules and identifies the malicious switch by using a thrift port. Fuzzy-based rule is framed to mitigate flow table modification attacks with the input values of changed flow rules.

- The methodology’s performance was tested on Facebook’s data center fabric using a Mininet emulator and P4 switch.

II. RELATED WORK

Our related studies emphasized OpenFlow and P4- based overflow and modification attacks. Yuan et al. [12] identified one critical flaw in SDN i.e. the limited size of the flow table, which is most likely to be exploited and may be quickly disabled by a flow table overloading attack. A QoS-aware mitigation strategy was proposed and developed an executable and feasible mathematical model by the authors. Different attack types that can be carried out on the remote and local control planes on the data plane were discussed by Yoon et al. [13]. In this study, a flow table modification attack has been addressed. Abdulkarem et al. [14] utilized the programmability of SDN and write an application program, which realized the mitigate of DDoS attacks against data plane, and reduced the interference of malicious traffic through real-time analysis of traffic. In [15], authors discussed low-rate DoS (LDoS) attacks against overflow attacks. They analyzed two types of attacks against table overflow and proposed small-flow and inport-flow analysis to mitigate the LDoS attack. In a recent work [16], to overcome flowtable overflow attack, the author uses the proactive flow rule number as the detection metric and uses a statistical method to support filtering out malicious flows. In recent years few authors vested their research interest on P4-SDN switch. In [17] authors have given a solution for flow table management by considering an idle timeout mechanism in P4 switches. Mahrach et al. [18] proposed a mitigation strategy for DDoS flooding attacks in the p4 switch. They proposed a solution to secure the data plane against intensity attacks using SYN cookies.

To the best of our knowledge, there has been limited research on data plane modification attack. The flow table modification attack is an unexplored research topic. In this study, a potential P4-based modification attack has been conducted and suggested mitigation framework, assuming the switch in the network is malicious.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

A. System Design

The structural procedure of establishing an SDN system is of 3 sub-phases which are discussed below.

1) *Initialization of the Topology*: The links associated with all the switches are connected and are initialized by the p4 forwarding protocol. The switches are initialized by connecting and assigning the thrift port p by `SIMPLESWITCH_API`. Thrift port is a communication interface used for control and management purposes between different components of a P4

Fig. 2: Framework of the proposed model.

switch. The Behavioral Model version 2 (BMv2) switches store the traffic flow information in packet capture log files.

2) *Allocation of flow rules*: The routes and flow tables among the switches are assigned and operated by the routing controller of the network. The routing controller provides the pathways between the forwarding devices based on the Routing Information Protocol (RIP) algorithm. The insertion of the flow table rule is accomplished based on these assigned paths. For the allocation of the flow rules in the switches `ConnectSwitch`, `Set_Default_Rules` functions were being utilized. It considers two cases for the issuance of regulations: (i) source and the destination host are connected to the same forwarding device, and (ii) connected to a different subnet.

3) *Configuration of flow rules*: The routing controller adds parameters like source IP address, destination MAC and port numbers to the rule. These parameters are further processed to generate the flow rule consisting of version, match key, action, runtime and the entry handle.

Some definition and assumptions introduced in this paper. **Definition 1 EFR**: The set of flow rules changed by the attacker is termed as external flow rules.

Definition 2 Holding time: Time required to halt the EFR by taking the required actions using the mitigation module. This metric quantifies the defending capability of the model against attacks.

Definition 3 Mild mitigation: This mitigation strategy used to delete EFR rules from flow table and load preexist flow rules.

Definition 4 Complete mitigation: This strategy deletes the `attacker_port`.

B. Detection and Mitigation Method

When the rules are altered, with the assistance of `RUNTIME_API.py`, important attributes like time and EFR of every forwarding device stored in the database are identified. In `SWITCH_API.py`, The malicious switch’s thrift port p_x is identified by mapping existing thrift ports to default and

termed as `ATTACKER_PORT()`. Then `SWITCH_API.py` redirects to `p4app.json`, identifies malicious switch links and then removes it. Fig. 2 shows an overview of the proposed framework.

To make the system effective, our mitigation module utilizes the fuzzy-based rule to identify the severity level of the attack. The membership function is particularly utilized for executing the element’s fuzziness in the fuzzy set. The input parameter has a trapezoidal membership function. The fuzzy set is used for solving the problem depending on its experience. The interval of the inputs is $[0,100]$, and outputs (μ) are within $[0,1]$. Based on the EFR range, the fuzzy inference engine generates the fuzzy rules in the form of an IF-THEN statement. The rules are given as: (1) If EFR% is 0-10%, then output: No Action. (2) If EFR% 10-20% then output: mild mitigation (3) If $EFR \geq 20\%$ then output: complete mitigation. It is important to note that the input ranges can be varied according to the requirements by the network administrator. However, we evaluate the proposed framework on the above input range. As mentioned in Fig. 2, the involvement of $A2$ refers to mild mitigation, and $A3$ refers to complete mitigation action. Mild mitigation strategy used to delete EFR rules from flow table and load preexist flow rules. The complete mitigation strategy used to delete `attacker_port`. It blocks the port and is restricted from transmitting packets among nodes in the network.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The implementation of the framework is performed on the P4-learning BMv2 operating system, and Mininet API. The algorithms were entirely programmed using Python. The machine is equipped with Intel i7 10th generation, UHD graphics, and 16 GB RAM. To mitigate the attack, we made changes in the backend Runtime API and Switch API so that any change in the flow rule and thrift port of the malicious switch would be known. The topology used in the experiment is similar to Facebook data centre fabric topology, which consists of different switches based on their positions and links [19]. The modified topology settings consist of 4 spine planes with 80 switches and 144 hosts as shown in Fig. 3. The total flow rules for the experiment were set as 7840, and the malicious switch injected EFRs based on the attack scenario.

The attack script changed a few flow rules such that the forward action changed to drop in between host $h1$ and host $h90$. It can be noted that both hosts belong to different network. The flow of packets would subsequently be halted throughout the network when flow rule changed. A scenario has been set such that the forward action changed to drop. Just before the attack, host $h1$ transmits 500 packets to $h90$. Before the attack, the flow rule was ‘forward’, so packets started to transmit. Fig. 5 demonstrates that during the transmission of the 39th packet, the attacker initiated the attack. Then packet dropping starts when the attacker modifies new rules. This interruption is incorporated into the overall holding time. Without an attack mitigation strategy, every packet got dropped

Fig. 3: Topology settings

till the 500 packets transmission which can be observed in Fig. 4a (yellow line). Conversely, utilizing the proposed mitigation approach, 38 packets were well received. The mitigation algorithm involves deletion of EFR and reloading default flow rules. It takes holding time to proceed it and partial packet loss occurred. After 14th second, normal packet transmission resumed between the two hosts as illustrated in Fig. 4a (green line).

A. Successive Multiple Attack and Holding Time

A successive multiple-attack experiment was conducted in a scenario where two additional attacks were initiated during the transmission packets. The mitigation module holds for a 3-second duration in response to three successive attacks occurring every 10 seconds. This involved the mild action when the EFR percentage fall within the range of 10 to 20 range. Consequently, this prompted the attacker to repeatedly inject malicious EFR values, allowing unauthorized network access through a compromised switch, as illustrated in Fig. 4a (depicted by the blue line). Implementing the mitigation strategy led to a consistent delay at each holding time interval. Subsequently, when EFR% varied from 15 to 25%, the mitigation module responded by triggering the deletion of the attacker’s port and reloading flow rules, employing a complete mitigation approach. This proactive action eventually results in no further attacks, as shown in green line of Fig. 4a.

The memory consumption (in megabytes) of increased malicious flow rules, represented as EFR%, in comparison to the original flow rules is illustrated in Fig. 4b. In this aspect, until 10%, there are no action and memory consumption equals each other. Further, there are different actions using fuzzy based on the trapezoidal membership function. Which states the deletion of EFR until 20%. Later on, deleting the malicious port from the network can be a feasible solution that decreases memory consumption.

To evaluate the efficacy of holding time, we escalated the attack rate (requests per second). Multiple attacks were generated by simultaneously increasing the number of switches

Fig. 4: Comparison between training loss using proposed method

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len=40 ip=10.0.23.90 ttl=59 DF id=28634 sport=0 flags=RA seq=34
win=0 rtt=27.6 ms
len=40 ip=10.0.23.90 ttl=59 DF id=28637 sport=0 flags=RA seq=35
win=0 rtt=23.9 ms
len=40 ip=10.0.23.90 ttl=59 DF id=28710 sport=0 flags=RA seq=36
win=0 rtt=20.3 ms
len=40 ip=10.0.23.90 ttl=59 DF id=28791 sport=0 flags=RA seq=37
win=0 rtt=7.8 ms

--- 10.0.23.90 hping statistic ---
500 packets transmitted, 38 packets received, 93% packet loss
round-trip min/avg/max = 5.3/11.8/28.6 ms

```

Fig. 5: Attack scenario during packet transmission.

Fig. 6: False PDR in successive multiple attacks

(k). In a moderate mitigation scenario we observed a linear increase in the holding time with the increased of k as shown in Fig. 4c. This trend indicates that the network can sustain itself for approximately 60 seconds when encountered with multiple attacks at $k=12$, irrespective of the attack rate.

Fig. 6 illustrates variations in key actions and packet delivery. The employment of fuzzy-rule-based mitigation techniques effectively reduces the EFR rate. It leads to diminished false rates from 5.55% to zero in the false Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR). Ultimately, this contributes to increased true PDR and accurate actions, enhancing the overall quality of service without compromising data integrity or security.

B. Attack Impact Analysis and Limitations

Flow rules within each switch are established utilizing the shortest paths, often guided by the RIP. Although it is hard to predict the existing rules and paths, but it creates the possibility of making new rules with knowledge of topology settings. During an attack, the packet flow in the entire network can be paused for at least $\max(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n)$ time where t_i is the time to update flow table rule. The attacker can take advantage of this by attacking the networks with multiple iterations. In multiple iterations, the average packet flow starts tending to zero as most of the flow rules will be modified to drop by the attacker.

As a new research finding, there are several issues to be further investigated. Primarily, limitations could be a longer time delay for searching malicious switches in a considerably larger dynamic real-time network. Secondly superfluous communication between the controller and the the switch may consume large resources, which may create other related issues such as the control plane resource depletion attack and link saturation attack. Third, during experimenting the framework treated all the switches in the network are equal. However, in practice, all switches have their own table space, different workload capabilities, etc. All these findings need to be taken into consideration for future system modelling.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The work represented a new potential flow table modification attack with a suitable mitigation mechanism in a P4-based SDN dataplane. After the attack is initiated, the changed flow rules are identified using the thrift port. Further, a mitigation mechanism is proposed using a fuzzy-rule-based technique that takes action against malicious flow rules. The mitigation mechanism takes action in accordance with changing flow rules. Two strategies such as mild and complete mitigation strategies to counter the attack. The overall methodology is simulated with a large data centre fabric in a Mininet environment with a P4 switch. Our future direction is to compress holding time using more impactful AI techniques, as the present world needs the best Quality of service (QoS), validate the solution in the P4 switch and improve real-time analysis of the network.

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